

The Sodium and Potassium Phenolates.

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The sodium and potassium phenolates have been prepared in a variety of ways. Potassium phenolate, for instance, was prepared (1) by heating phenol with solid potassium hydroxide (Hartmann, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1877, (ii), **16**, 38), (2) from phenol and potassium whilst a current of hydrogen was passed (*loc. cit.*, p. 36); (3) by mixing solutions in alcohol of phenol and potassium ethoxide and evaporating (de Forcrand, *Ann. Chim. Phys.*, 1893 (vi), **30**, 61); (4) by boiling phenol with a solution of potassium carbonate (Baumann, *Ber.*, 1877, **10**, 686). These methods have various disadvantages: the first gives crude material: the second and third are expensive: the third is also troublesome because the last traces of alcohol are not easily removed from the phenolate; moreover, these methods are unnecessary except in special cases.

A simple method of preparing potassium phenolate, as the authors found, is to dissolve phenol in an ordinary aqueous solution of potassium hydroxide and then to add a concentrated solution of the same alkali: crystalline potassium phenolate is precipitated and can be isolated in a relatively pure state.

This method is comparable with the precipitation of a metallic chloride from solution by means of hydrochloric acid. It is a general method; the authors used it for the preparation of a number of sodium and potassium phenolates. These phenolates have definite melting points: when the melting point is low the phenolate separates as a liquid, *e.g.*, sodium *o*-cresolate. In no case did the phenolate contain water of crystallisation.

It is to be observed that the solubility of a phenolate is an important property that may be useful in the isolation of a phenol. This is illustrated in the next paper, where two phenolic substances, namely 3-nitro- and 5-nitro-salicylic acids, are separated and purified by means of their potassium compounds.

No difficulty was found in obtaining derivatives from these substances: potassium phenolate was converted into phenyl benzoate and into diphenyl ether: sodium *p*- and *m*-cresolates were converted into the respective benzoates.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The composition of the solutions that were used in the experiments is shown in the following table:—

	Alkali in water (100 c.c.)	
	NaOH	KOH
Ordinary solution	20 g.	28 g.
Strong ,,	100 g.	100 g.
Very strong ,,	...	200 g.

Usually it was sufficient to dissolve the phenol in the minimum amount of ordinary solution and then to add the strong solution. In special cases it was necessary, the phenolate being comparatively insoluble, to dilute the ordinary solution before use: the phenolate being comparatively soluble, to precipitate by means of the very strong solution: the phenolate having a low melting point, to cool by means of a freezing mixture; these cases are mentioned as they arise.

The crystalline precipitate was collected, using a Buchner funnel, with the aid of the pump, and was drained for some time so that by absorption of moisture from the air the crystals were freed from the adhering alkaline solution. At the same time foreign material, such as suspended matter from the alkaline solutions, was found to collect in a layer below. The crystals were next pressed on a porous tile and the tile was kept in a desiccator.

For analysis the phenolate, having been pressed again on a clean, dry, porous tile, was converted into sodium or potassium sulphate.

Only the usual precautions were taken in observing the melting points which may therefore be slightly low.

Sodium phenolate was obtained as needle-shaped crystals, m.p. 59-60°. (Found: Na, 19.6. C_6H_5ONa requires 19.8 per cent.).

Potassium phenolate was obtained as small needles that changed into plates, m.p. 103-104°. (Found K, 29.4. C_6H_5OK requires 29.6 per cent.).

Sodium o-cresolate was obtained as a liquid that solidified below 0°.

Potassium o-cresolate was obtained with difficulty as needle-shaped crystals. It is very hygroscopic.

Sodium p-cresolate was obtained as long needles that changed into glistening plates, m.p. 123-125°. (Found: Na, 17.8. C_7H_7ONa requires 17.7 per cent.).

Potassium p-cresolate was obtained as glistening plates, m.p. 92°. (Found: K, 26.2. C_7H_7OK requires 26.7 per cent.).

Sodium m-cresolate was obtained, using diluted sodium hydroxide for dissolving, as glistening plates, m.p. 92-94°. (Found Na, 7.5. C_7H_7ONa requires 17.7 per cent.).

Potassium m-cresolate was obtained, using very strong potassium hydroxide for precipitating, as small prisms, m.p. about 36°. It is very hygroscopic. (Found: K, 26.9. C_7H_7OK requires 26.7 per cent.).

Sodium m-xylenolate formed slowly as minute crystals, m.p. 41-43°. (Found: Na, 15.7. C_8H_8ONa requires 16.0 per cent.).

Potassium m-xylenolate was obtained only as a liquid.

Sodium p-xylenolate was obtained as glistening plates, m.p. 83°. (Found: Na, 16.1. C_8H_8ONa requires 16.0 per cent.).

Potassium p-xylenolate was obtained, using very strong potassium hydroxide for precipitating and using a freezing-mixture, as granular crystals, m.p. 35°. (Found: K, 24.4. C_8H_8OK requires 24.4 per cent.).

Sodium guaiacolate was obtained, using diluted sodium hydroxide solution, as small crystals, m.p. 120°. (Found: Na, 15.6. $C_9H_8O_2Na$ requires 15.7 per cent.).

Potassium guaiacolate was obtained, using diluted potassium hydroxide solution, as small crystals, m. p. 168°. (Found: K, 24.0. $C_9H_8O_2K$ requires 24.1 per cent.).

Sodium eugenolate was obtained, using diluted sodium hydroxide solution for dissolving, as shining plates, m.p. 115°. (Found: Na, 12.6. $C_{10}H_{11}O_2Na$ requires 12.4 per cent.).

Potassium eugenolate was obtained, using diluted potassium hydroxide solution for dissolving, as prismatic crystals, m.p. 128°. (Found: K, 19.3. $C_{10}H_{11}O_2K$ requires 19.3 per cent.).

Sodium α -naphtholate was obtained, on cooling, as small crystals, m.p. 44-45°. (Found: Na, 14.4. $C_{10}H_7ONa$ requires 13.8 per cent.).

Potassium α -naphtholate was obtained only as a liquid.

Sodium β -naphtholate was obtained, using diluted sodium hydroxide for dissolving, as small plates, m.p. 120°. (Found: Na, 13.9. $C_{10}H_7ONa$ requires 13.8 per cent.).

Potassium β -naphtholate was obtained as small plates, m.p. 38-40°. (Found: K, 21.5. $C_{10}H_7OK$ requires 21.5 per cent.).

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